

Algorithmic Two-Step

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Introduction

My procedure for creating art algorithmically involves two steps:

1. *Either* algorithmically generating a “base” image, which may be, for example, a simple geometric figure, line drawing, grayscale image, etc. *or* selecting a base image, which may be a photograph, hand drawing, cartoon, etc.
2. Applying various transformations to achieve a complex image.

The second step is performed with my own app. This app can apply an arbitrary number of different transformations to an image, such as switching from cartesian to polar coordinates or vice versa, rotating the image, segmenting the image into parts that are then rearranged, applying various transformations and distortions, etc.

Step 1: Langlet’s SHAPES algorithm

For this paper I’m going to use an algorithm created by biochemist/crystallographer Gérard Langlet¹. In 1993 Langlet published a paper entitled “Building the APL Atlas of Natural Shapes.”² This paper featured his **SHAPES** program which, with just a handful of inputs, is able to produce a seemingly endless series of shapes, ranging from those found in flowers and other plants, to crystals, microscopic molecular and biological structures, familiar geometric shapes like the Koch snowflake and the roulette curves created by Spirograph, and works of visual art. Figures 1 and 2 suggest the variety of shapes that can be obtained with **SHAPES**.

¹ <https://archive.vector.org.uk/art10001730>

² Gerard Langlet. *Building the APL Atlas of Natural Shapes*. APL '93 Proceedings of the International Conference on APL. New York, NY: ACM (1993).

Figure 1

Figure 2

SHAPES takes six numeric arguments that together determine the shape of an image. It generates a set of points which can subsequently be rendered as a black-and-white line drawing, as shown in Figures 1 and 2. Unless otherwise specified, all the line segments in a **SHAPES** figure are of the same length. As a practical matter I rewrote Langlet's APL program in Dyalog (a variant of APL) and then translated the Dyalog version into Matlab. The translation into Matlab hopefully makes the **SHAPES** algorithm more accessible, but I actually chose Matlab for two other reasons:

- its built-in “app designer,” which makes it very easy to create an app with buttons, pull-down menus, radio buttons, toggle switches, text boxes, lamps, dials, knobs, sliders, etc.
- the availability of its add-on “toolboxes,” such as Image Processing and Signal Processing, which provide much of the functionality I needed to create my digital art app. I would otherwise have had to produce this functionality myself.

Adding initial colors

To make artistic use of a **SHAPES** figure I first need to add initial colors. This can be done automatically in both Dyalog and Matlab. Dyalog will correctly add specified line, fill, and background colors to an image. Figures 3 and 4 are examples of three-color images generated by my Dyalog version of **SHAPES**. Two-color images with just line and background colors are easy to make in Matlab, but if a fill color is desired the initial line-drawing must be a network consisting only of triangles.³ As can easily be seen, Figure 1 is not a network of triangles. This is always the case with **SHAPES** figures. As a result Matlab's built-in line-drawing function can

³ The actual technical condition which must be satisfied is “Delaunay triangulation.” A discussion of this condition can be found in https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Delaunay_triangulation

provide only line and background colors.

Figure 3

Figure 4

With an app such as MS Paint it is possible to hand-color a Step 1 image with more than three initial colors. Figures 5 and 6 are examples of this approach.

Figure 5

Figure 6

It should be noted that in most cases the choice of initial colors is not important. It is only necessary that there be as many *different* colors as desired. The final coloring of an image is

usually done after all the operations in Step 2 have been completed. My app provides a function that “borrows” a color scheme from another image, such as a painting or photograph, and automatically transfers it to the new image. The app also provides over 100 fixed palettes, any of which can be selected and applied after Step 2.

Step 2: Transformations

To make an object of aesthetic interest from a **SHAPES** figure I apply my digital art app. Two of the possible transformations my app can perform are shown in Figures 7 and 8. In Figure 7, a **SHAPES** figure has been transformed by a sequence of operations including “inversion” (see Figure 22 below). The center of the new coordinate system is the upper left corner. In Figure 8, a **SHAPES** figure is used as a motif that appears several times in modified forms within the image.

Figure 7

Figure 8

See the **Appendix** for more details on transformations.

Optional post processing

If desired, a final touch can be achieved by, for example, applying one or more G'MIC-Qt⁴ filters that can be added to GIMP.⁵ The resulting image can have a slick character that disguises the process by which it was made. Figure 9, for example, is an unretouched image, while figure 10 has been modified with the G'MIC-Qt “local processing” filter. The differences between the two images are relatively small. Figure 9 is simply flat, while Figure 10 suggests a three-dimensional space containing some fruits or vegetables and leaves.

⁴ An open-source framework for digital image processing, available from gmic.eu

⁵ A free image processing app available from www.gimp.org .

Figure 9

Figure 10

Gallery

Figures 11-18 were produced by the two-step procedure described above using different base images and transformations.

Figure 11

Figure 12

Figure 13

Figure 14

Figure 15 shows the result of randomly displacing the R, G, and B planes of an image relative to one another. This operation can simultaneously add both new colors and new shapes to an image.

Figure 15

Figure 16

Figure 17

Figure 18

Concluding comments on method

I view my digital art as being in the spirit⁶ of painter Francis Bacon. Speaking about his art, Bacon stated that “I want a very ordered image, but I want it to come about by chance.”⁷ The word “chance” is doing a lot of work here. One would like to know *how* chance could produce Bacon’s unquestionably “very ordered” images. I think the explanation can be found in another of Bacon’s observations: “All painting is an accident. But it’s also not an accident, because one must select what part of the accident one chooses to preserve.”⁸ This immediately brings the artist back into the picture in a key role: *selecting* from whatever may occur when, as Bacon expresses it, he “splashes the stuff down”⁹ on the canvas. All of the artist’s knowledge, experience, and skill come into play in making such selections.

Where Bacon the painter is looking for unpredictable effects due to the peculiarities of specific brushes, paints, canvas, and manual gestures, the “accidents” in my digital art are generally based on a digital source of uncertainty, typically a random number generator. The output of a random number generator is used to generate accidents in two ways:

1. creating random images of different kinds (e.g., Figures 1 and 2)
2. randomly modifying some aspects of an image, e.g., color, geometry, texture, etc. (e.g., Figures 11-18)

My app has 25 Step 1 base image-generating algorithms, 36 base image libraries, 32 “preset” algorithms for performing Step 2 operations, and 56 functions from which new Step 2 algorithms

⁶ But not in the financial reality of, e.g., his Lucian Freud triptych, which sold for over \$142 million USD.

⁷ Bacon, Francis. Quoted in: Gruen, John. *The Artist Observed: 28 interviews with contemporary artists*. A Cappella Books. 1991. ISBN: 1556521030.

⁸ Ibid.

⁹ Ibid.

can be created. Most of the functions take one or more random inputs, which provide the opportunity for accidents in the sense that the exact nature of the output images they produce cannot be known in advance¹⁰. As with Bacon's approach, the selection of what is to be preserved in an image is up to me. Such images thus have the same dual nature as Bacon's accident-that-isn't-an-accident images

The artistic method I've described here is completely general. It doesn't depend in any way on Langlet's **SHAPES** algorithm or on my app and the specific operations it provides. A base image can be an image file of any standard kind, and the artist can employ whatever transformations yield the desired results. My app simply codifies a practice I arrived at through trial and error. It provides a convenient interface to the set of operations I wish to perform.

Appendix: Geometric Transformations

This section briefly describes some of the transformations that I use frequently in Step 2. A base image, Figure 19, is shown with three different transformations (Figures 20-22). What each transformation does can be seen by noticing where the black, white, and gray squares in the base image end up in the transformed image.

Figure 19. Base image

Figure 20. Cartesian to polar coordinates

¹⁰ The ranges of the various random inputs have been fine-tuned after much experimentation. Each random input is allowed to vary within upper and lower limits that are known to produce satisfactory results.

Figure 21. Polar to cartesian coordinates

Figure 22. "Inversion"

Figure 23 is another base image, a grid representing the cartesian coordinate system. Figures 24-26 are distortions of the coordinate system that I use frequently.

Figure 23. Base image

Figure 24. Pincushion distortion

Figure 25. Barrel distortion

Figure 26. "Annular rotation" distortion

The use of a distorted coordinate system was partly inspired by D'Arcy Thompson's classic study *On Growth and Form*¹¹. Figure 27 shows how a particular distortion can transform a

¹¹ D'Arcy W. Thompson. *On Growth and Form*. (1917). Revised edition published by Cambridge University Press. 1992 and 2014. Online ISBN: 9781107325852

natural form into another form that also occurs in nature.

Figure 27. From *On Growth and Form* by D'Arcy Thompson.